

Grimmiaceae family mosses as natural passive samplers of metal pollution in urban-industrial atmospheres from the Bilbao Metropolitan area

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Abstract

In analytical chemistry, biomonitoring is known as the methodology, which consider the use of living organisms to monitor and assess the impact of different contaminants in a known area. This type of monitoring is a relatively inexpensive method and easy to implement, being a viable alternative to be developed in sites where there is no infrastructure/instruments for a conventional air quality monitoring. These organisms, having the capability to monitor the pollution, are also known as natural passive samplers (NPSs), since they are able to identify possible contamination sources without the need of any additional tool. In this work, a multianalytical methodology was applied to verify the usefulness of *Grimmia* genus mosses as NPSs of atmospheric metal pollution. Once mosses were identified according to their morphology and taxonomy, their ability to accumulate particulate matter (PM) was determined by SEM. EDS coupled to SEM also allowed to identify the main metallic particles deposited and finally, an acid digestion of the mosses and a subsequent ICP-MS study define more precisely the levels of metals accumulated on each collected moss. The study was focused on six sampling locations from the Bilbao Metropolitan area (Biscay, Basque Country, north of Spain). The experimental evidences obtained allowed to propose *Grimmia* genus as NPS of atmospheric metal pollution and to identify the atmospheric sources that contribute to the emission of the airborne particulate matter rich in metals, evaluating in this sense the atmospheric metal pollution of the selected locations.

36 **Keywords:** *Grimmia* genus mosses; Bilbao Metropolitan area; natural passive sampler;
37 atmospheric metal pollution; SEM-EDS; ICP-MS.

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40 According to the economic growth that different worldwide regions have experimented in
41 the last decades, the related industrial activities have caused a direct negative impact on
42 their surrounding environment. This negative impact is closely related with the increase of
43 atmospheric pollution. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), in 2016, the
44 91% of the world's population lived in regions where PM_{2.5} concentrations exceeded 10
45 µg/m³, which is the limit value acceptable for human health suggested by the WHO Air
46 Quality Guide (World Health Organization, 2016). This same report indicates that the
47 highest PM_{2.5} levels were observed in the North and West Africa regions and in the Middle
48 East with concentrations ranging from 122 to 204 µg/m³ and 148 to 188 µg/m³,
49 respectively. The human overpopulation of megacities is the main cause of the
50 disproportionate increase of these concentrations (Krzyzanowski et al., 2014). The
51 particulate matter (PM) corresponds to a set of solid particles and/or liquid small clusters
52 emitted to the surrounding and coming from different anthropogenic sources (e.g.,
53 industrial and livestock processes, domestic fuel uses, residential heating, mining activities,
54 forest fires, fossil fuel combustions and vehicular traffic) (Lelieveld et al., 2015; Haikerwal
55 et al., 2015; Zhang and Batterman, 2013; Querol et al., 2007).

56 Specifically, heavy metals in atmospheric particulate matter (HMAPM) emitted to the
57 atmosphere is a serious problem for human health (Li et al., 2013; Davidson et al., 2005),
58 food security (Sun et al., 2017), ecological systems (Grantz et al., 2003) among others.
59 These HMAPM, due to their dispersion capacity, have a direct high toxic effect in the
60 biosphere (Nriagu et al., 1990), increasing the risks of contamination in particular
61 ecosystems (Szyrkowska et al., 2018; Udayakumar et al., 2014). In the last years, the
62 knowledge of concentrations of these pollutants (both, in urban and rural areas) has been an
63 aim of interest for researchers from different scientific fields (Zhai et al., 2014; Wang et al.,
64 2013; Vianna et al., 2011; Kumar et al., 2013). According to many biological systems,

65 HMAPMs can be incorporated into eukaryotic cells and cause structural damage to
66 endomembrane and enzymatic systems, which are directly related to the cell growth,
67 metabolic and energy production, detoxification, and damage repair processes (Tamás et
68 al., 2014; Sharma et al., 2009; Demir et al., 2014). In the literature, there are many works
69 describing that heavy metals such as As, Cd, Cr, Pb and Hg have a toxic effect in the
70 production of reactive oxygen species and, consequently, responsible for significant
71 damage in algae cellular structures (Dao and Beardall, 2016), plants (Shahid et al., 2014),
72 fish (Eroglu et al., 2015), mollusks (Radwan et al., 2019) and humans (Karri et al., 2016).
73 Likewise, these metal exposures can cause DNA mutations, cell cycle mechanisms
74 derangements, tumor progression or apoptosis (Guzel et al., 2012; Hartwig et al., 2002). In
75 many ecological systems, high levels of heavy metals can cause disturbances to ecosystems
76 or represent a fatal threat to biodiversity (Aktar et al., 2010; Blake and Goulding, 2002;
77 Tchounwou et al., 2012). In fact, the high possibility of metal bioaccumulation in the food
78 chain can cause a subsequent transfer to other terrestrial biosphere compartments, such as
79 water and land, increasing its risk of poisoning (Jara-Marini et al., 2009; Croteau et al.,
80 2005).

81 Moreover, the loss of air and water quality promote a direct damage in the biodiversity and
82 biota systems (Kampa and Castanas, 2008; Mohapatra and Biswal, 2014). As it has been
83 explained by some authors, depending on the PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations, they can
84 cause health problems to human population, including cough and breathing problems (Zeng
85 et al., 2016), respiratory tract irritation (Huang et al., 2016), heart disease and respiratory
86 problems (Van Eeden et al., 2013; Hogg and Van Eeden, 2009), development of mental
87 retardation and kidney damage (Quadros and Marr, 2010), neurotoxicity and premature
88 death due to cardiac or pulmonary conditions (Kelly and Fusell, 2012; Duruibe et al., 2007;
89 Järup, 2003).

90 Due to these human health problems related with HMAPMs, the monitoring and controlling
91 processes of pollutants that are closely related with atmospheric contamination becomes
92 essential. In the last years, the use of natural passive samplers (NPS) has incremented (Lin,
93 2015; Wannaz et al., 2013) as an analytical alternative procedure to other conventional
94 ones, in order to monitorize the air quality. In this way, as an analytical routine process and

95 efficient tool for diagnosis, monitoring and air quality management, lichens and mosses are
96 being considered worldwide as NPSs (Ogunkunle et al., 2016; Salo et al., 2012;
97 Chakraborty and Paratkar, 2006). They allow the evaluation of air pollution by HMAPMs
98 deposited or accumulated directly in their tissues (Boquete et al., 2014; Schröder et al.,
99 2010).

100

101 Since the 70's, mosses have been used regularly in large-scale monitoring studies,
102 providing key information on the spatial and temporal dynamics of HMAPM depositions
103 (Onianwa, 2001). The use of mosses as NPSs of atmospheric pollutants on temporal and
104 spatial changes is defined by two methodological approaches, passive or active
105 biomonitoring. For the first case, the mosses growing in a particular area are collected
106 directly and analyzed (Baltrėnaitė et al., 2014). For the case of active samplers, moss
107 samples are collected from relatively unpolluted areas; then, they are cleaned, selected and
108 treated before they are exposed at different polluted environments (Boquete et al., 2013;
109 Fernández et al., 2002; Cesa et al., 2006). In recent years, air quality biomonitoring using
110 moss samples has been studied through the implementation of different analytical
111 techniques, such as Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA), for the evaluation of trace
112 elements deposition in *Sphagnum girgensohnii* samples (Madadzada et al., 2019); Atomic
113 Absorption Spectrometry (AAS) in *Haplocladium microphyllum* (Zhou et al., 2017) and
114 *Fabriona ciliaris* and *Leskea angustata* moss samples (Macedo-Miranda et al., 2016); and
115 Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) in *Orthotrichum*
116 *lyellii* samples (Donovan et al., 2016).

117

118 In this work, we present a multianalytical methodology to evaluate the capacity of *Grimmia*
119 genus mosses collected in urban and urban-industrial environments of the Bilbao
120 metropolitan area (Biscay, Basque Country, north Spain) to act as NPS of atmospheric
121 metal pollution. Moreover, the second aim of this work was also to, once obtained the
122 experimental results, identify the anthropogenic sources that can contribute to the emission
123 of the airborne particulate matter rich in metals, and therefore to evaluate the atmospheric
124 metal pollution of the selected locations. For that, first of all the collected mosses were
125 identified based on morphological descriptions and taxonomic keys. Their capacity to trap

126 and accumulate PM was evaluated through SEM observations and a rapid screening using
127 EDS technique coupled to SEM allowed to determine the main metallic particles deposited
128 on the mosses from each location. Finally, an ICP-MS analysis of the acid extracts of the
129 mosses assisted the quantification of metals at $\mu\text{g/g}$ and ng/g levels accumulated in the
130 mosses.

131

132 **2. Experimental procedure**

133 *2.1. Sampling locations*

134 Moss samples were collected at six different sites (S) located in the Bilbao Metropolitan
135 area (Basque Country, north of Spain) (see Fig. 1 and Fig. S1 from Supplementary
136 Material). To select the sampling points, those locations with identified sources of
137 anthropic activities that contribute to HMAPM emissions were taken into consideration.
138 The first sampling point (S1) was San Julián neighborhood, in the municipality of Muskiz,
139 located in the north-west of Bilbao Metropolitan area ($43^{\circ}19'59.6''\text{N}$ $3^{\circ}06'47.2''\text{W}$). This
140 sampling point is mainly influenced by a petroleum refinery, road traffic and steel
141 galvanized industry (see Fig. S1A for details of the samples collected and Fig. S2 for
142 details about the sampling location, both from Supplementary Material). Samples were
143 collected from a stone wall located at few meters from the road. The second sampling point
144 (S2) was the northwest façade of historical building from Getxo (Province of Biscay)
145 located close to the sea ($43^{\circ}20'28.1''\text{N}$ $3^{\circ}00'46.6''\text{W}$). This sampling point is mainly
146 influenced by marine aerosol, a nearby petrochemical refinery, an electric power generation
147 plant and ship traffic coming from the Abra Bay and Bilbao port activity (see Fig. S1B for
148 details of the samples collected and Fig S3 for details about the sampling location, both
149 from Supplementary Material). Samples were collected from the railings located on the
150 north face of the construction a few meters from the road. The third sampling point (S3)
151 was the Lutzana neighborhood of the municipality of Barakaldo located in an urban
152 environment ($43^{\circ}17'09.3''\text{N}$ $2^{\circ}58'33.3''\text{W}$). Samples were collected from a concrete wall
153 close by the train track and road. This sampling point is mainly influenced by the industrial
154 activity related to the distillation of tar, road traffic and rail transport (see Fig. S1C for

155 details of the samples collected and Fig. S4 for details about the sampling location, both
156 from Supplementary Material). The fourth sampling point (S4) was a concrete wall with
157 rock from the Scientific and Technological Park of Biscay, located in the municipality of
158 Zamudio, 10 km far way from Bilbao (43°17'34.7"N 2°51'47.2"W). This sampling site is
159 mainly influenced by air traffic (due to its proximity to the Bilbao International Airport)
160 and road traffic (see Fig. S1D for details of the samples collected and Fig. S5 for details
161 about the sampling location, both from Supplementary Material). The fifth sampling point
162 (S5) was located in Basauri, in the southeast part of the Bilbao Metropolitan area,
163 (43°13'35.6"N 2°53'19.7"W). This municipality is mainly influenced by different
164 surrounding iron and steel industry activities, road traffic and rail transport (see Fig. S1E
165 for details of the samples collected and Figs. S6A and S6B for details about the sampling
166 location, both from Supplementary Material). Samples were collected from a stone wall at
167 few meters from the road. Finally, the sixth sampling point (S6) was located in Amorebieta-
168 Etxano. This municipality is located out of the Bilbao Metropolitan, concretely in the
169 Duranguesado region (43°13'18.5"N 2°44'05.1"W). This sampling site is mainly influenced
170 by road traffic. Samples were collected from a stone wall next to the railway station.
171 Moreover, a thermal power plant is located 2 km far away from the sampling location (see
172 Fig. S1F for details of the samples collected and Fig. S7 for details about the sampling
173 location, both from Supplementary Material).

174 *2.2. Moss sampling and pretreatment*

175 A total of 18 samples (3 samples per each sampling point) were collected according to the
176 sampling protocol suggested by (Harmens et al., 2010). In each sampling point, three
177 secondary points were established in an area of 25 m² x 25 m². Samples were collected at
178 least 100 m away from the main roads and railways, at least 50 m from local roads and 200
179 m from local industries and populated areas (Maxhuni et al., 2016). The taxonomic
180 identification of mosses was based on the recommendations given elsewhere (Crandall-
181 Stotler and Bartholomew-Began, 2007; Sérgio et al., 2007; Casas, 1991). For
182 morphological descriptions, photographs were taken under a stereoscope microscope with a
183 Olympus SZ6 model camera. In the laboratory, the apices of the shoots (0.5-1 cm) were cut

184 from the moss plants using a scalpel. The use of apical tissue ensures experimental material
185 standardization in terms of contaminants (Carballeira and López, 1997). Prior to the ICP-
186 MS analysis and in order to remove the moisture content of mosses, the samples were dried
187 at 45°C for 24 hours.

188

189 *2.3 Instrumentation*

190

191 Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) was used for the quantification of
192 the major, minor and trace elements in the 18 moss samples. Prior to the elemental analysis
193 of the samples, an acid digestion was performed, using 0.5 g of dried moss sample and 6 ml
194 of 2:2:2 HNO₃ (69%): H₂O₂ (30%): H₂O (Milli-Q water) mixture. The HNO₃ concentration
195 in the acid extracts was reduced up to 1% using Milli-Q water. In addition, a solution
196 containing 10 µg·L⁻¹ of Be, Sc, Ge, In, Re and Bi was added as internal standard. The
197 internal standards and ICP-MS calibration standards solutions were prepared from 1000
198 mg·L⁻¹ stock solutions of Alfa Aesar (Specpure®, Plasma standard solution, Germany)
199 inside a class 100 clean room. All solutions were prepared using Milli-Q quality water and
200 employing PL 20–200 µL and PL 500–5000 µL micropipettes (Eppendorf, Hamburg,
201 Germany). Calibration standards and samples dilutions were prepared using a Mettler-
202 Toledo XS205 analytical balance (Columbus, OH, USA) with an accuracy of ± 0.00001 g.

203 The elemental analysis of the extracts was performed using the NexION 300 ICP-MS
204 (Perkin Elmer, Massachusetts, USA) in a class 100 clean room. The 99.995% argon used
205 was supplied by Praxair (Madrid, Spain). ²⁷Al, ⁴⁴Ca, ⁸⁸Sr, ⁹⁸Mo, ¹¹⁴Cd, ¹²⁰Sn, ¹²¹Sb, ¹³⁸Ba,
206 ¹⁸⁴W, ²⁰²Hg and, ²⁰⁶Pb + ²⁰⁷Pb + ²⁰⁸Pb isotopes were determined in standard mode and ²³Na,
207 ²⁴Mg, ³⁹K, ⁴⁷Ti, ⁵¹V, ⁵²Cr, ⁵⁵Mn, ⁵⁶Fe, ⁵⁹Co, ⁶⁰Ni, ⁶⁵Cu, ⁶⁶Zn, ⁷⁵As, ¹¹¹Cd isotopes were
208 determined in collision mode with He in order to eliminate possible polyatomic
209 interferences. The plasma conditions such as the nebulizer argon flow, the torch position
210 and the voltages of the lenses were optimized before each measurement session aspirating a
211 standard solution of 1 ng·mL⁻¹ of Mg, Rh, In, Ba, Pb and U. The nebulizer flow was
212 optimized obtaining a compromise between sensitivity and low oxides level (less than 2.5%
213 for the CeO/Ce ratio). Finally, the data were acquired and analyzed for the element

214 quantitative analysis using the NexION 1.5 software (Perkin Elmer SCIEX™, Ontario,
215 Canada). For each element, the average value and its standard deviation (s) were calculated.
216 The errors associated to quantitative values in Tables and Figures are expressed as 1s. Table
217 S1 from Supplementary Material shows the experimental conditions used for the ICP-MS
218 analysis.

219 In parallel to the ICP-MS analyses, SEM-EDS was also employed for the analyses of
220 deposited particles in the different morphological parts of the mosses. In order to obtain
221 satisfactory results, the mosses apical segments were previously dried in an oven at 45°C
222 during 24 h as it has been described in the 2.2 section. After that, the samples were
223 mounted on an aluminum pin stub fixed to a carbon tape. For the image acquisition, the
224 abaxial and adaxial surfaces of the apical mosses surfaces samples were coated with gold to
225 ensure their conductivity and therefore, to obtain microscopic images of good quality. For
226 the SEM-EDS analyses, an EVO®40 Scanning Electron Microscope (Carl Zeiss NTS
227 GmbH, Germany) coupled to an XMax Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectrometer (Oxford
228 Instruments, Abingdon, Oxfordshire, United Kingdom) was used. SEM images were
229 obtained at low vacuum employing an acceleration voltage of 30 kV and a 10 to 400 µm
230 working distance for the image acquisitions and elemental analysis (single point and
231 imaging) respectively. Different magnifications (reaching up to ×6800) were used for
232 secondary electron images and an integration time of 50 s was employed to improve the
233 signal-to-noise ratio. The EDS spectra were acquired and treated using the INCA suite
234 software (version 4.13) (Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, Oxfordshire, United Kingdom).

235

236 **3. Results and Discussion**

237 *3.1. Morphological and taxonomic aspects of collected mosses*

238 Morphological and taxonomic analysis of the mosses collected at the six sampling sites
239 indicated a greater predominance of the Grimmiaceae family. The *Grimmia orbicularis*
240 species was identified at the S1 sampling site, while the *Grimmia pulvinata* species was
241 identified at S2, S3 and S4 sampling points. In addition, in S5 and S6, the *Grimmia*
242 *ramondii* species was identified (see Table S2 from Supplementary Material).

243 The genus *Grimmia* is widely distributed, generally growing on mixed substrates, such as
244 sand-covered rocks, old walls or mortars (Maier, 2010) (see Fig. S1 from Supplementary
245 material). In Fig. 2, stereoscopic photographs of analyzed mosses can be observed.
246 Regarding to the species *G. orbicularis* and *G. pulvinata*, both species have similar
247 morphological characteristics (i.e., lanceolate phylloids, keeled, recurved margin, acute apex
248 with long hyaline hair) (Long, 2008; Hastings et al., 2004; Staples et al., 2004), but they
249 can be differentiated by their capsule. In *G. orbicularis* the capsule is smooth, rounded and
250 with a rounded operculum; while in *G. pulvinata* the capsule is striated, ellipsoidal and with
251 a pointed operculum. In the case of *G. ramondii*, it has dark green to ochre long stems,
252 lanceolate phylloids, slightly bent towards the apex, keeled, normally without hyaline hair
253 (see Figs. 2E and 2F).

254 The morphological aspects of the species found in the sampling sites, their wide
255 geographical distribution and ability to grow in the form of cushions with dense phylloids in
256 different types of substrates (see Fig. S1 from Supplementary Material and Table S2), as
257 well as, the arrangement of their branched lateral gametophytes derived from a periquecial
258 outbreak, could confer to these biological matrix the ability to be used as NPS in the
259 monitoring processes and control of air pollution in different scenarios (Harmens et al.,
260 2013; Mazzoni et al., 2012; Zechmeister et al., 2004; Onianwa, 2001).

261 As mentioned, the genus *Grimmia* is widely distributed throughout the world. Specifically,
262 *Grimmia pulvinata* is a common species in Europe. However, there are few works related
263 to the use of the genus *Grimmia* as a passive sample of metallic atmospheric contamination.
264 At the level of studies related to the evaluation of the accumulation capacity of heavy
265 metals in endemic mosses of countries in temperate and cold zones, they have been widely
266 addressed. Specifically, *Sphagnum*, *Hypnum*, *Helycomium*, *Orthodicranum*, *Tortula* genera,
267 among others, have been reported (Zhong et al., 2019; Belivermiş et al., 2008; Davies et al.,
268 2007; Aziz and Khdir, 2016; Adrović et al., 2017). Most of these investigations correspond
269 to active biomonitoring studies (implementation of moss bags or other supports) (Cortis et
270 al., 2016). Elsewhere, the species *Grimmia dissimulate*, also cosmopolitan, has been
271 mentioned as a good candidate to measure deposition and accumulation of metals in a

272 tropical country (Zimbabwe), with the implementation of active monitoring (Gaza and
273 Kugara, 2018).

274 Based on scientific reports, the only notable work that presents the use of a species of genus
275 *Grimmia*, and concretely *Grimmia pulvinata*, as a natural passive sample is the one of
276 Natali et al. (2016). In this work, they only present the quantitative values of the metal
277 concentrations in *Grimmia pulvinata* obtained by the TXRF technique.

278 *3.2. Evaluation of the ability of Grimmia genus mosses to act as* 279 *natural passive samplers of atmospheric metal pollution*

280 In order to verify the ability of *Grimmia* genus mosses to act as NPS of HMAPM, SEM
281 observations of the apical tissue samples of native mosses collected from the six sampling
282 points were conducted in order to verify the presence of deposited PM. Moreover, the
283 elemental composition of the visualized particles was also determine by EDS. Once
284 verified that mosses are able to accumulate particles, the atmospheric heavy metals
285 pollutions of each sampling point was evaluated according to the kind of metals and their
286 concentrations accumulated in each moss from each location. For that, a previous extraction
287 of the metals in the PM and a subsequent quantification of them by ICP-MS was
288 conducted. This technique allow us to understand the main anthropogenic emission sources
289 related with the different studied areas, such as industrial activities, fossil fuel combustion,
290 road traffic emissions etc.

291 *3.2.1. Study of the particulate matter deposited on moss samples by* 292 *SEM-EDS*

293 The PM deposited on adaxial and abaxial surfaces of mosses phylloids from the collected
294 sampling points were analyzed by means of SEM-EDS (see Fig. S8 from Supplementary
295 Material). S1, S2, S3, S5 and S6 sampling points showed the highest accumulation of
296 particulate matter in their respective tissues of the mosses (see Figs. 3 and 4). The SEM
297 microphotographs presented in Fig. S8 from Supplementary Material show the random
298 distribution of particles, heterogeneous in size and shape, in the phylloids. In Table 1,

299 examples of the particle size on each moss from each sampling location together with their
300 elemental composition and position in the phyllodes of the mosses (adaxial or abaxial
301 surface) are presented. Although the greatest presence of PM deposited on the phyllodes
302 occurs on the adaxial surface, a predominance of smaller metallic PMs takes place on the
303 adaxial surface of the phyllodes, which indicates that this part of the phyllodes located in
304 the canopy of the moss cushions serve as receptors for particulate material from the
305 surrounding atmosphere. However, the presence of metallic PM less frequently on the
306 abaxial surface of the phyllodes shows that for each particular case (sampling sites) the
307 mosses serve as natural passive samplers of atmospheric pollutants.

308 Most of the deposited particles showed a wide range of diameters ranging from 3-4 μm to
309 70-100 μm (see Figs. 3 and Fig 4). Most of the particles show the presence of Al and Si
310 (see Table 1), suggesting the presence of aluminosilicates (of Na, K, etc. depending on the
311 element associated).

312 In the moss from S1 sampling point, a 50 μm particle deposited on the adaxial surface of
313 phylloid composed by Ca and F was detected (see Fig. 3A), suggesting the presence of
314 calcium fluoride. This compound is closely related with the gasoline refining process
315 (Kvande and Drabløs, 2014; De la Campa et al., 2011).

316 In many occasions, observations under SEM allowed us to identify aggregates (clusters) of
317 individual particles. Example of it is the association of particles detected on the specimen
318 from S1 sampling location showing the presence of Ca, C, K, O, Fe, Na, Al, Si and S (see
319 Fig 3B). The detected elements suggest the possible aggregations of iron oxide, potassium/
320 calcium/sodium aluminosilicates and even sulfates or sulfur oxides. This cluster can be
321 related with the emissions of petrol refinery (Bozlaker et al., 2013; Freije, 2015; Xiao et al.,
322 2010), and anthropogenic source that exert influence in the S1 sampling area (see Fig. 1).

323 Additional clusters also show the presence of heavy metals, among additional lighter
324 elements. This is the case of the particles shown in Fig. 3C and 3D, deposited on abaxial
325 surface of phylloid of *G. pulvinata* from the S3 sampling location. The particle of Fig. 3C
326 corresponds to a Ti-rich agglomerate of Ca, K, V, Fe, Mg, Al; and the one shown in Fig.
327 3D to a cluster which includes C, K, N, Cr, Cu, Na, P and Cl in its composition. Ti-rich

328 particulates can be related to atmospheric emissions coming from tar manufacturing
329 processes (e.g., crushing, mixing and loading of carbonaceous material) (Kaminsky et al.,
330 2008). Indeed, PM emissions rich in TiO_2 is distinctive of volatile material generated in
331 coke production furnaces (Montilla et al., 2002). On the other hand, PM including calcium
332 silicate-iron oxide aggregates, together with elements such as C, K, N, Cu, Na, P and Cl,
333 could suggest a mixed origin, such as soot contribution (C), suspended earth/dust
334 deposition and Cr input (see Fig. 3D). The PM rich in Cr has been associated with
335 industrial activities related to the use of Cr-compounds for coal oxidation processes
336 (Barnhart, 1997; Xu et al., 2004), vehicular and rail traffic (Abdel-Latif et al., 2012). These
337 anthropogenic contributions are present in the S3 sampling site from which these mosses
338 were collected (see Fig. S4 from Supplementary Material).

339 In the Fig. 3E, a particle with a diameter lower than $50 \mu\text{m}$ deposited on the adaxial surface
340 of phylloids of *G. ramondii* collected in S5 sampling point can be observed. It must be
341 highlighted that the elemental composition (mainly Fe and O apart from Ca and Si), size
342 and angular shape of the particle suggest a possible geogenic origin of the emission
343 (Rudnick and Gao, 2003; Mico et al., 2015), probably belonging to iron oxide (Fe_xO_y) or
344 oxyhydroxide ($\text{FeO}_x(\text{OH})_y$), emitted by steel industry. S5 sampling point is placed just in
345 front of an iron and steel manufacturing company (less than 100 meters) (see Fig. S6B from
346 Supplementary Material).

347 Smaller particles were also detected on the phyllodes. As an example a $5 \mu\text{m}$ angular
348 particle deposited on the phylloids of *G. ramondii* from S5 sampling location can be
349 mentioned (see Fig. 4A). Apart from Ca, Fe, Si and O, this particle showed the presence of
350 additional heavy metals such as Zr and Sc. In the metallurgical of steel process Zr is
351 extensively used due to its chemical characteristics as a material resistant to corrosion
352 phenomena in acid atmosphere (Zhang et al., 2018) and it is also used when different
353 corrosive agents are employed (Li et al., 2013). Moreover, in a $2 \mu\text{m}$ spherical particle (see
354 Fig. 4B) from the same sampling area, apart from additional elements, heavy metals such as
355 Fe, Cr and Zn were present. Therefore, the iron emissions conducted by the iron-steel
356 industry located close to the sampling point are once more confirmed. The presence of
357 other chemical compounds cannot be ruled out, such as iron oxides, chromium and

358 scandium compounds, zirconium silicates, etc., which are also related to alloy production
359 processes using Ni, Al and Fe compounds as additives in steels and metallurgical processes
360 (Owoade et al., 2015; Srivastava et al., 2009; Gioda et al., 2004). The presence of Cr could
361 be related to the surface treating processes of the steel industry, since the chromium plating
362 process (electroplating) is a very common process related again with corrosion protections
363 processes (Edy et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2019).

364 In the Fig. 4C and 4D, the presence of additional small particles on the adaxial surface of
365 phylloids of the sample from the S5 sampling locations of circa 1 μm and 5 μm in size are
366 observable. These particles show the presence of rare earth elements such as La-Ce-Nd
367 cluster apart from others such as Ca, C, K, O, Si, Al and Sr. These metallic particles may be
368 related to additives used for the combustion of diesel motors (Morillas et al., 2019), and
369 usually are related with the stabilization of diesel engine fuels (Gradeff et al., 1989). The
370 same kind of particles were detected on the S6 sampling point. It is noteworthy, that this
371 last sampling point is located just next to the road that crosses the town of Amorebieta and
372 also next to the train crossing. Next to the sampling point, all the vehicles must stop till the
373 crossing gate opens, and consequently the ones that use diesel engines could emit this
374 type of rare-earth metal particles, as described elsewhere (Dai et al., 2016). Additionally,
375 these particles are also related to their use as additives in hybrid trains that use both electric
376 and diesel engines (Soudagar et al., 2018; Dhal et al., 2018; Peiro et al., 2011).

377 To clarify how the metals can be distributed in a specific particle or cluster, SEM-EDS
378 mappings were also obtained. An example of it are the EDS maps of the particle
379 aggregration deposited on the phylloids of *G. pulvinata* from the S2 sampling location (see
380 Fig. 5). This is a good example of a metallic particle aggregation, showing the main
381 presence of Pb, apart from other elements in less proportions, such as Al, K and Si, or even
382 Ca and Fe. Concretely, among the individual microparticles, a quite pure 30 μm Pb particle
383 was detected in the mapped area. The small metallic fragments surrounding this particle
384 could indicate a previous fragmentation of a much larger particle. In additional works
385 carried out in the same sampling site, Pb-particles were also detected (Morillas et al., 2019;
386 García-Florentino et al., 2018). In this case, the source of this element can be related with

387 the emission from coal derived an old power station plant, which worked with carbon the
388 60's and other anthropic activities mentioned above.

389 The non-detection of heavy metals on specific PMs from mosses of certain sampling
390 locations does not imply that they are not present on the PM. It should take into
391 consideration that the limit of detection of the EDS technique for the heavy metals ranges
392 from hundreds to thousands of $\mu\text{g/g}$ depending on the atomic number of the metal.
393 Therefore, the use of an additional technique (e.g., ICP-MS) able to detect those metals at
394 lower concentrations (few $\mu\text{g/g}$ or ng/g) becomes essential.

395 *3.2.2. Quantification of metals in moss samples by ICP-MS*

396 Table S3 from Supplementary Material shows the concentrations of elements at ppm ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
397 levels in all the analyzed moss samples. Elements that showed highest concentrations in the
398 acid extract of the mosses were Al, Ba, Pb, Ti, Cu, Zn, Mn and Fe. Since in the extraction
399 of metals from the biological tissues hydrofluorhidric acid was not employed, Si was not
400 determined by ICP-MS. As can be seen, in the Fig. 6 and in the Table S3 from
401 Supplementary Material, their average concentration decreases in the following order; Fe>
402 Al> Zn> Mn> Ti> Cu> Ba> Pb. Highest concentrations of these elements were detected in
403 the S3 sampling point.

404 S1 and S3 sampling points present the highest concentrations of Ba (57.0 ± 1.0 and 108 ± 10
405 $\mu\text{g/g}$, respectively) as it is shown in Fig. 6. In S1 sampling point, the most important source
406 of pollution could be the petrol refinery (see Fig. S2A from Supplementary Material),
407 however as samples were collected, as in the case of S3, at a distance of less than 2 and 12
408 meters, respectively, the influence of the road traffic cannot be discarded (see Figs. S4A-B
409 from Supplementary Material). Various studies suggest an important source of Ba coming
410 from cars brake pad (Sternbeck et al. 2002; Khan et al., 2012; Carrero et al., 2013;
411 Grigoratos et al., 2015), thus the continuous impact of road traffic in both S1 and S3
412 sampling locations could be the responsible of the increase in Ba concentration
413 accumulated in the moss samples.

414 Special attention should be paid to the high Pb concentration in S2 moss sample (1077 ± 16
415 $\mu\text{g/g}$) being almost 10 times higher comparing with the additional samples obtained from
416 the rest of the locations. As it has been mentioned, Pb-particles and in some cases almost
417 pure ones were detected also by SEM-EDS. In previous studies carried out in the same
418 building from which the moss samples were extracted in the S2 sampling area (Morillas et
419 al., 2019, García-Florentino et al., 2020), it was observed an unusual high presence of Pb.
420 Concretely, in the work developed by García-Florentino et al., Pb was identified
421 accumulated in the inner areas of black crusts formed on the same construction (García-
422 Florentino et al., 2020). Its presence in the inner areas of the black crust suggested that this
423 heavy metal was accumulated at the beginning-middle stage of black crust formation.
424 Indeed, it was impossible to detect Pb in the outer part of the analyzed black crusts. This
425 experimental evidences lead to conclude that the lead emission event took place years ago.
426 Considering that in this case, the analyzed mosses could grow up years ago, the Pb detected
427 in them can be also attributed to past and not recent emissions. In the work developed by
428 García-Florentino et al. and thanks to the isotopic ratio analysis (García-Florentino et al.,
429 2020) the origin of the accumulated Pb was connected to emissions coming from coal
430 burning. In this way, the S2 sampling area is located close to an old power station plant
431 which worked with carbon since the 60's. Additionally, in the literature, some authors point
432 out that this element can be related to the emissions from smelters industries (Wu et al.,
433 2012), lead batteries (Sun et al., 2017), lead paints (Báez et al., 2007), or even municipal
434 solid waste incineration (Tan et al., 2006; Khan et al., 2012). Therefore, these additional
435 sources cannot be ruled out.

436 Regarding other heavy metals, the highest concentrations of Ti, Cu and Zn were detected in
437 the S3 sampling point, a quite polluted area comparing with the other. In this way, the
438 concentrations obtained were 4 times higher for Ti ($478\pm 22 \mu\text{g/g}$), 9-10 times higher for Cu
439 ($225\pm 17 \mu\text{g/g}$), and 8-9 times higher for Zn ($1750\pm 150 \mu\text{g/g}$). This result agree with the
440 observations done by SEM-EDS, since it was possible to detect easily the presence of Ti
441 and Cu in the moss sample from the S3 sampling location. The presence of Cu could be
442 linked with local industrial activities such as oil and hydrocarbon production (Pandey and
443 Madhury, 2014), modified tars and carbon black oil (Mu et al., 2012; Freije et al., 2015),

444 cement processing (Ogunkunle and Fatoba, 2013), non-ferrous Cu alloy processes (Qing et
445 al., 2015), or even due to a flux component in Fe metallurgy (Boyd et al., 2009). Some
446 authors describe that Zn is closely related with the presence of ZnO particles and it is
447 noteworthy that is widely used as an additive coat for steel casting (Chia et al., 2008; Ma et
448 al., 2018).

449 Finally, it must be highlighted that the concentration of Mn and Fe presents a similar trend
450 in all the sampling points (see Fig. 6), being S2, S3 and S5 those ones with the highest
451 concentration (Mn: 287.2 ± 6.5 , 985 ± 72 and 357 ± 13 $\mu\text{g/g}$, respectively; Fe: 5344 ± 97 ,
452 12300 ± 400 and 5260 ± 370 $\mu\text{g/g}$, respectively). Once more, the quantitative results agree
453 with the SEM-EDS observation since Fe was easily detectable in the particles accumulated
454 on the mosses from those locations. Some authors explain that these metals usually form
455 rolled cluster particles (Morillas et al., 2016). On the one hand, the presence of these high
456 Mn concentration could be connected to its use in the chemical industry as an oxidant agent
457 (Itahashi et al., 2018), as an alloy agent for special steels (Jorge et al., 2019), or even as
458 specific Mn alloy employed in materials for needles and railroad track changes instruments.
459 Particularly, the S5 sampling point is just in front of a steel industry and the train railways,
460 therefore both of them corroborate this possible emission source. Regarding the Fe particle
461 emissions, in S2 sampling point the high Fe concentration could be related to oil refining
462 processes (Freije et al., 2015; Li et al., 2009) from the surrounding industries. For the S3
463 sampling point, in addition to being influenced by vehicular traffic and rail transport, this
464 location is strongly affected by the coal tar distillation and the use of Fe in this process
465 (Wang et al., 2019). Finally, the high Fe concentration detected in the S5 sampling point
466 could be related to the direct influence of the metallurgical industry and their emissions
467 because of the steel production.

468 Apart from metals at ppm levels, additional ones at ng/g levels and not easily detectable by
469 EDS were quantified also by ICP-MS in apical tissue samples of native mosses collected at
470 the different sampling sites (see Fig. 7 and Table S4 from Supplementary Material).
471 Concretely, Li, Sr, Ag, Sn, Sb, W, Hg, Co, As, Cd, V, Cr, Ni and Se were detected. Once
472 more, the moss from S3 sampling point presents the highest concentrations of almost all of
473 these minor/trace elements (e.g., Li, Mo, Ag, Sn, Cd, Co, As and Ni). Similarly, high

474 concentrations of W, Hg and V at S1 sampling point, Sr and As at S2 sampling point , Sr at
475 S4 sampling point , Cr and Se at S5 sampling point and Sb at S6 sampling point were also
476 identified.

477 These elements are probably related to both, anthropogenic activities and geogenic origin.
478 For instance, the S3 sampling point, in addition to car/trucks and rail traffic, is
479 characterized by the presence of an important coal distillation industry, which can
480 contribute, during its production processes (e.g., coal tar, naphthalene, creosote, anthracene,
481 oil, among others) with most of the mentioned elements (i.e., Ag, Sn, Sb, W, Hg, Co, As,
482 Cd, V, Cr, Ni and Se). Additional authors (Mu et al., 2012) confirmed these conclusions
483 characterizing heavy metal emissions related to coking processes in Taiyuan (China),
484 through the qualitative and quantitative assessment of forest soils exposed to emissions
485 coming from coke plants in southern Poland (Rachwał et al., 2015) and the evaluation of
486 Hg emissions from coal combustion in China (Wang et al., 2000).

487 On the one hand, high concentrations of W, Hg and V were quantified on the moss from S1
488 sampling point. As it has been explain before, this site is near to an oil refinery, thus its
489 production processes are probably a source of atmospheric emissions of coke vapors with
490 high content in V and Hg (Ötvös et al., 2003). In fact, oil combustion processes in heated
491 furnaces represent an important source of V₂O₅-rich gases (Xiao et al., 2010; Pereira et al.,
492 2010; Reddy et al., 2005), as well as of derivatives from phenylmercurial compounds that
493 are potentially toxic (Pandey and Madhury, 2014; Bozlaker et al., 2013). W could be
494 present as trace metal in rocks (Khan et al., 2012) and Sr can be present in the marine
495 aerosol. In this sense, S2 sampling point is directly affected by marine influence (Morillas
496 et al., 2018). Regarding Cr and Se, in the S5 sampling point, their presence could be
497 connected to activities of the local metallurgical industry, since they are widely used in
498 stainless steel alloys (Qing et al., 2015; Quan et al., 2014). Finally, the highest
499 concentration of Sb at the S6 sampling point is probably related to the chemical processes
500 developed in semiconductor industries (Eom et al., 2006), alloy production and electric
501 welding, as well as combustion by diesel train engines (Sarvi et al., 2009; Maricq, 2007).

502 **4. Conclusions**

503 The experimental evidences obtained through the application of the analytical methodology
504 based on the combination of SEM-EDS and ICP-MS support the usefulness of *Grimmia*
505 genus mosses as NPSs for the atmospheric metal pollution being a good alternative to other
506 active sampling methodologies to determine the metals present as PM in the surrounding
507 environments.

508 The obtained results showed a clear evidence that the different heavy metals detected in the
509 PM trapped and accumulated by the mosses are closely related to anthropogenic activities
510 (road traffic, train and ships traffic emissions, iron-steel industries, petroleum refinery,
511 power plants, tar destilation industries etc.).

512 In the multianalytical methodology, SEM-EDS application revealed as a good tool to
513 identify those most impacted environments by atmospheric metal pollution through a rapid
514 screening of the composition of the PM accumulated in the mosses. The evaluation of
515 metals concentrations by ICP-MS allowed to definitely conclude which are the main
516 metallic particles accumulated on the mosses in each sampling points inside Bilbao
517 metropolitan area. Remarkable is the high concentration of Pb in S2 sampling point, being
518 10 times higher than in the additional sampling points. In this case and thanks to the
519 relation with other experimental evidences in additional supports (PM accumulated in black
520 crusts growing on building materials), it was possible to confirm that this area was highly
521 impacted by Pb emission in the past. These results were corroborated with SEM-EDS
522 imaging analyses in where specific Pb particles were observed (average size of 30 μm).
523 The mosses from S3 sampling point also show a remarkable higher concentration of Ti, Cu,
524 Zn, Mn and Fe, comparing with the additional sampling point.

525 Since most of the mentioned heavy metals showed concentrations 8-10 times higher than in
526 the rest of the sampling points, it was possible to conclude that the S3 sampling point
527 (Lutxana, Barakaldo) is the sampling point with a higher atmospheric metal pollution. On
528 the contrary, the less polluted one was S4 sampling point (Scientific and Technological
529 Park from Biscay in Zamudio).

530 According to the experimental obtained evidence we can conclude that *Grimmiaceae*
531 familia mosses, such as *G. orbicularis*, *G. pulvinata* and *G. ramondii*, are good candidates

532 to be used as NPSs of atmospheric metal pollution. This conclusion was extracted
533 analyzing the deposited PM in the mosses.

534 The conclusions extracted for this specific area in the Basque Country could be expanded in
535 the future with additional studies using the same genus of mosses but located in other kind
536 of environments with diverse climatological conditions and diverse anthropogenic sources
537 that can contribute to the emission of metallic particles to the atmosphere. Moreover, in
538 those mosses that show high concentrations of specific heavy metals, an evaluation of their
539 influence in the normal functioning of these mosses should be conducted. For that, it will
540 be necessary to assess if the mentioned heavy metals have been assimilated/incorporated
541 into the tissues of the mosses, through a proper cleaning process of the deposited PM and
542 an appropriate analytical methodology that will reveal the bioaccumulated metals in the
543 mosses.

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928 **Figure Legends**

929 **Figure 1.** Satellite location of sampling sites: A) San Julián de Muskiz neighborhood (S1);
930 B) Punta Begoña Galleries in Getxo (S2); C) Lutzana neighborhood in Barakaldo (S3); D)
931 Scientific and Technological Park in Zamudio (S4); E) Basauri (S5); F) Amorebieta (S6).

932 **Figure 2.** Stereoscopic photographs of mosses collected at sampling sites: A) *G.*
933 *orbicularis* from S1 sampling point; B) *G. pulvinata* from S2 sampling point; C) and D) *G.*
934 *pulvinata* from S3 and S4 sampling points; E) and F) *G. ramondii* from S5 and S6 sampling
935 points.

936 **Figure 3.** SEM-EDS single point-by-point analysis showing the presence of A) 50 μm
937 aggregate of calcium fluoride deposited on adaxial surface the phylloids of *G. orbicularis*
938 collected in S1 sampling point (San Julian de Muskiz); B) 3-4 μm aggregate of iron oxide,
939 aluminosilicates, sulfur oxide with K/Na/ deposited on the adaxial surface the phylloids
940 from *G. orbicularis* collected in S1 sampling point; C) 3-4 μm aggregate of titanium oxide
941 and Ca/K/V/Fe/Mg/Al deposited on abaxial surface the phylloids from *G. pulvinata*
942 collected in S3 sampling point (Lutzana); D) 3 μm aggregates of calcium silicate or
943 aluminosilicates, iron oxide with C/K/N/Cr/Cu/Na/P/Cl deposited on abaxial surface the
944 phylloids from *G. pulvinata* collected in S3 sampling point and E) 30-40 μm aggregate of
945 calcium silicate or aluminosilicates with high metallic iron content deposited on adaxial
946 surface the phylloids from *G. ramondii* collected in S5 sampling point (Basauri).

947 **Figure 4.** SEM-EDS single point analysis showing the presence of A) 3 μm aggregate of
948 iron oxide, zirconium silicate and aluminosilicate and Sc/Ca/Zr deposited on abaxial
949 surface the phylloids from *G. ramondii* collected in S5 sampling point, B) 2 μm aggregate
950 of iron oxide, calcium silicate and C/Cr/Mn/Zn/Mg deposited on abaxial surface the

951 phylloids from *G. ramondii* collected in S5, C) and D) 1 and 5 µm aggregates of
952 aluminosilicate, iron oxide K/C/La/Ce/Nd/Sr/P deposited on adaxial surface the phylloids
953 from *G. ramondii* collected in S6 sampling point.

954 **Figure 5.** SEM–EDS mapping of PM deposited on adaxial surface the phylloids from *G.*
955 *pulvinata* collected in S2 sampling point (Punta Begoña Galleries).

956 **Figure 6.** Concentrations of major elements of mosses collected in different sites of Bilbao
957 Metropolitan area (Biscay, Basque Country, north of Spain).

958 **Figure 7.** Concentrations of minor elements of mosses collected in different sites of Bilbao
959 Metropolitan area (Biscay, Basque Country, north of Spain).

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Mosses as natural passive samplers for biomonitoring of atmospheric heavy metal pollution.
- SEM-EDS to detect and identify the presence of metallic particles.
- ICP-MS quantification of heavy metals in atmospheric particulate matter deposited on mosses.
- Identification of the most impacted locations from the Metropolitan Bilbao area.

Sampling points

Table 1. Examples of elemental composition of particles deposited on the adaxial or abaxial surface of the phyllodes in relation to their size (diameter).

Sampling point	Particle diameter (μm)	Elemental composition	Adaxial surface of phylloid	Abaxial surface of phylloid
S1	50	F, O and Ca, Al, Si (At lower proportions)	X	
	2	Fe, O and Al, S (At lower proportions)	X	
	8	Mg, Al, Si	X	
S2	35	Pb, Fe and Ca, O, Al, Si, K, Ca (At lower proportions)	X	
	5	Fe, O and Ca, Al, Si, K (At lower proportions)	X	
S3	3	Ti, V, Cu		X
	28	Si, Al, K, Mg		X
	3	Cr, Fe and P, Cl (At lower proportions)	X	
	2.5	Al, Si, Ca, Mg, Na		X
	5	Fe, Zn, Al, Mg, Si		X
	2	Cr, Fe, Cu	X	
S4	16	Al, Si, K, O	X	
	40	Ca, Si, K, Al, Mg, Na	X	
S5	8	Fe, O and Si, Al, Mg, Ca (At lower proportions)	X	
	40	Fe, Ca, Si, O, Al		X
	5	Zr and Sc, Fe (At lower proportions)	X	
	20	Al, Si, Ca, Mg, Na	X	
	2	Fe, Mn, Cr, Zn, O and Ca, Mg, Si (At lower proportions)	X	
S6	1-5	La-Ce-Nd	X	
	15	Al, Si, Ca, Mg, Na		X
	2	La-Ce-Nd and Ca, C, K, O, Si, Al, Sr (At lower proportions)		X
	30	Al, Si, Ca, Mg, Na	X	

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Barranquilla, 23rd June 2020

To whom it may concern,

I testify on behalf of all co-authors that our article submitted to *Chemosphere journal* with the title: "*Grimmiaceae family mosses as natural passive samplers of metal pollution in urban-industrial atmospheres from the Bilbao Metropolitan area*"

The authors declare that the following description is true:

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